

INFLUENCE OF VORTEX GENERATOR ON AUGMENTATION OF HEAT TRANSFER IN THE CHANNEL

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Abstract

Many researchers have looked into the passive approach to enhancing the flow of heat in tube heat exchange devices. Some of them attempted to alter the surface by making dimples or using wire coils with various cross-sections, while others focused on core fluid disturbance by using insert geometries like twisted tapes. In the present research, testing was performed to strengthen heating in channels with distinct arrangement of vortex generator. A method for analysis of fluid movement and transfer of heat in a channel with vortex generator using CFD tool was also developed. Under the different mass flow rates, average wall temperatures for steady state circumstances were calculated and compared with test results. It highlights how the addition of vortex generator to the test surface improves forced convection heat transfer.

Keywords: Channel, Enhancing Thermal Performance, Parametric Investigation, Vortex Generator.

1. INTRODUCTION

A focus of research for researchers is the use of vortex generators to create turbulence in thermal exchangers to improve heat transmission. The main objective of this kind of work is to decrease the size and expense of exchangers for heat while increasing their thermo-hydraulic performance through the use of various passive heat transfer improvement techniques. Most often, air is transported in round, square, or rectangular tubes. The optimum performance for air volume handled per perimeter distance comes from a circular channel. There is a smaller amount of material needed to achieve the same capacity as a square or rectangular channel. There are two possible cross sections for these channels: orthogonal (rectangular or square) or non-orthogonal (trapezoidal), in which case the resulting flow is incredibly complex. The channels may occasionally be waved or corrugated in the direction of the stream, or even constructed with ribs, to help a speedier transition to turbulence [1]. By introducing geometrical elements into the channel at irregular intervals, turbulent flows can be created to improve heat transmission from the surface to the fluid. With turbulent flow, the channel's temperature can be controlled. Turbulent channel flows, which are frequently seen in a numerous industrial uses, such as inter-coolers, recuperates, cooling channels in combustion chambers, methods for cooling gas turbines, modular exchangers of heat, and nuclear reactors, also require improved predictive performance. Different techniques for cooling a modern gas turbine blade are shown in Fig.1. Turbulators on the blade's ribs line serpentine cooling tunnels. Through pin-fin cooling with ejection, the blade's trailing edge is cooled while jet impingement cools the blade's front edge. Although the techniques used to cool the vanes and the blades are similar, the vanes' and the blades' patterns of heat transmission are very unlike. The blades spinning cause a shift in the coolant flow in the channels. As a result, consideration must be given to how rotation impacts the enhancement of internal heat transmission [2].

Fig 1: Schematic of a modern gas turbine blade with common cooling techniques [2]

The study of heat transfer improved surfaces is of tremendous interest for a variety of industrial and transportation uses, as well as in other technical fields including microelectronics and biology. Enhanced surfaces are frequently used as the core element of a modular exchanger for heat. It is effective to artificially roughen the surface or add turbulence boosters to increase the rate at which the moving fluid transfers heat through a channel [3].

2. NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

The analysis was performed using CFD code. The stages in the analysis included the construction of the geometry, meshing, applying boundary conditions, solution, and post-processing. The geometry was developed and meshed while the channel was constructed and divided into teeny components. The definition of the domain and the assignment of boundary conditions follow. A suitable solver is then used to import the system and solve it using a variety of physical models. During post-processing, numerous parameters are predicted in order to get more details about the results. Using the aforementioned steps and the appropriate model, the current system was examined.

To analyse the square channel's features for fluid movement and transfer of heat, the 3D axisymmetric square duct was considered as a continuum. A hexahedral element with map meshing approach was used for efficient surface meshing, and the rectangular computational domain of geometry was used to simulate the square channel using GAMBIT. The model was imported into Fluent after the boundary conditions had been set.

In the current investigation, the velocity at the entrance was input as a result of the mass flow rate, and 0 gauge pressures were considered at the exit. It was believed that a constant source of heat flow would be provided by the top and bottom walls. The commercial code contains a variety of solver models, such as those for radiation, phase change, and turbulence. The reference velocity used in this study denotes higher turbulence in the flows. As a result, analysis was performed using the standard κ - ϵ model.

2.1 Numerical Findings and Interpretation

Figure 2 shows the X-Velocity contour plot for a straightforward plate at the channel's centre. It highlights how the formation of boundary layers causes velocity to decrease close to the wall. Fig.3 displays the channel's X-Velocity contour plot at central section. It shows how a negative velocity zone is established behind the ribs and turbulence is produced in the ribcage. The formation of the recirculation zone in the ribcage is indicated by negative velocity. Fig.4 displays the X-Velocity contour plot for a channel with connected ribs that are staggered in the channel's midsection. It demonstrates how a negative velocity zone is established behind the ribs and turbulence is produced between the ribs.

Fig 2: X-Velocity contour plot for Plain plate with no ribs at Re=19434

Fig 3: X-Velocity contour plot for Inline attached Rib at Re=19434

Fig 4: X-Velocity contour plot for Staggered attached Rib at Re=19434

Figures 5 and 6 show, for different channel layouts, the relationship between Nusselt number and Reynolds number as well as the correlation between average wall temperature and Reynolds number. Average wall temperature values decrease and Nusselt number values increase as Reynolds number increases for all test surfaces taken into account. For the same heat input, the inline attached rib configuration performs superior to the alternative two arrangements in terms of average wall temperature values and Nusselt numbers, but worse than plain channel. It proves that a channel with an inline linked rib arrangement transmits heat more efficiently.

Fig 5: Variation of average wall temperature with Reynolds number

Fig 6: Variation of Nusselt number with Reynolds number

3. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSES

The setup for the experiment consists of the heat exchange module, air flow bench, test plates, thermocouple wires, temperature indicator, and water-manometer. Heat is pushed convectively moved from a heated test surface to a cool fluid in the heat exchange module, which is a crucial part of the complete experimental setup. The heat exchange module consists of a 500x50x50 mm³ aluminium channel lined with both plain and ribbed test plates. Three situations were considered: a channel with a straightforward plate, a channel with attached ribs arranged in a straight line, and a channel with attached ribs arranged staggered.

The ribs' duct height to rib height ratio is 0.2, their rib height to rib pitch ratio is 10, and their cross sections are square (w=e). The top and bottom of the test plate were screwed with a 500x50x2 mm³ rectangular strip heater. In order to regulate the heater's electric power supply, wattmeter connections were connected to the power socket. The top and bottom of the test plate each have an attachment for insulation and a heater. Insulation was present on the test plates' other two smooth surfaces. Glass wool served as insulation. As a result, the test plate's ribbed surface where convective transferring heat to the airstream occurs was the sole part of the test plate to which the air stream was exposed. The heat exchanger module's top and bottom surfaces were riveted with galvanised iron ribs. In order to test the forced convection heat transfer measures, the heat exchange module was created.

An appropriate air flow bench was built to test forced convection heat transfer. In the open area above the test surface, air had to be forced to move at the necessary rate. A blower, a flow control valve, an orifice meter, and a pipe that carries forced air from the blower outlet to the heat exchange module's intake make up an air flow bench. A blower with a 1.0 HP motor was used for the current work. The air flow rate across the test surface was controlled by a manually operated regulating valve. Orifice meter was intended to measure the volume flow rate of air at the regulating valve. To measure the pressure gradient across the orifice-metre in centimetres of water column difference, a U-tube water manometer was added. Air was transported through a metal pipe from the heat exchange module's input to the blower outlet (made of mild steel). The blower's round exit required the usage of the pipe, which had a circular cross section. Fig. 7 provides a schematic representation of the experimental setup and a good understanding of the air flow bench used for the forced convection heat transfer measurements.

Fig 7: Schematic of the experimental set-up

In eight different locations on the test surface for a variable air flow rate and heat input, the temperatures were measured using temperature indicators. The input and output air temperatures of the heat exchange module were noted. The Newton's law of cooling was used to compute the coefficient of heat transfer, which indicated that the heat flow from the surface to the fluid was proportionate to the temperature difference between the two. A pipe was used to connect the blower output and the heat exchange module in the air flow bench in order to carry the forced air from the blower to the heat exchange module. The pipe next to the blower output had a flow-controlling valve attached to it to regulate the airflow.

Air was brought to the heated test portion through a pipe that was about 2 meters long to permit fully developed flow. In order to gauge the regulated air flow rate in the pipe, an orifice metre was installed next to the regulating valve. The orifice-metre was coupled with a water manometer. A water manometer gives the pressure variation in centimetres of water column across the orifice-metre. An air flow bench was connected to the heat exchange module constructed as stated in the preceding section in order to force the air parallel to the ribbed test surface. The strip plate heater, which was fixed to the top and bottom test plates, was connected to the power outlet via the wattmeter. Wattmeter measurements were modified to apply the required heat input to the test plate. Copper-Constantan thermocouple wires that had been calibrated were used to measure temperature. Provisions are made on the test surface to protect the thermocouple connection. Moreover, measurements of the air temperature were made at the input and output of the heat exchange module. Image 1 displays the experimental setup.

Image 1: Experimental set-up

3.1 Experimental Outcomes and Analysis

The experimental findings about heat transport in a duct with various rib configurations were reported. The results are shown as average wall temperature and Nusselt number calculated for various Reynolds numbers. The results of the experiment are illustrated visually in Figs 8 and 9, which show how, for various duct layouts, the average wall temperature and Nusselt number fluctuate with Reynolds number and Reynolds number, respectively. It has been shown that when Reynolds number increases, average wall temperature values decrease and Nusselt number values increase for all test surfaces taken into account.

The inline attached rib layout had lower average wall temperature values and greater Nusselt numbers when compared to the other two arrangements. The average wall temperature values for plain channel were likewise higher under the same operating conditions. It proves that a channel with an inline linked rib arrangement transmits heat more efficiently.

Fig 8: Variation of average wall temperature with Reynolds number

Fig 9: Variation of Nusselt number with Reynolds number

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experiments results are compared with the CFD findings. Figs. 10 and 11 respectively depict the average wall temperature in relation to the Reynolds number and the Nusselt number in relation to the Reynolds number for the three cases. It clarifies that there is significant consistency between the experimental and CFD results. The maximum errors are 2.34 percent for average wall temperature and 2.25 percent for Nusselt number, respectively.

Fig 10: Average wall temperature Vs Reynolds number

Fig 11: Nusselt number Vs Reynolds number

5. CONCLUSIONS

The CFD technique is used to examine different channel and forecast velocity distribution, temperature distribution, and flow pattern. CFD results and experimental data are compared to develop the analytical procedure. The results of the experiment show that the rate of heat transfer from the test surface increases along with the mass flow rate of the flowing fluid. It also shows how the test surface's addition of ribs enhances forced convection heat transfer. Results from CFD exhibit good agreement with those from experiments. The three-dimensional square channel results show that for both inline and staggered designs, the

recirculation zone behind the ribs grows as the Reynolds number increases. The inline attached ribs have a stronger recirculation zone than the staggered attached ribs.

Nomenclatures

pp	Plane Plate
IAR	Inline Attached Rib
SAR	Staggered Attached Rib

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